

RISK ASSESSMENT OF THE DECISION IN REGARDS OF CORONA VIRUS IN ROMANIA

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Abstract

Purpose – *The corona virus is a situation generated by the globalization process. Therefore, the risk evaluation of the pandemic situation used to manage a global crisis is directly linked to the conference theme.*

Methodology/approach - *The methodology used is the classic approach of the Failure Mode and Effect Analysis in 5 steps.*

Findings – *The findings are all the risks resulting from evaluation of the decision done in the pandemic situation. Also, a new domain for FMEA application is resulting from this paper.*

Research limitations/implications – *The main limitation of the research is that the paper is referring only to the first stage of the pandemic. The further waves of the virus and post pandemic situation is not in the scope of this FMEA analysis.*

Practical implications – *The practical implication are possible further actions defined in case of the unacceptable risks.*

Originality/value – *The authors contribution is a total new use case for a risk evaluation tool. The FMEA analysis is used usually in the technical domain, but it's applicability can be extended. On the other hand, there is a risk evaluation of the decision in regards of corona virus crisis management that can help the establishment too handle this situation.*

Key words: Covid-19, Pandemic, FMEA

Introduction

System components analysis, Function Analysis, Failure Analysis, Risk Assessment and Optimization. After the first step it results a tree diagram with all the actors involved. The second step consists in evaluation of the role of each actor. The next step is the analysis of all the possible errors that actors can do. The fourth step is the analysis of the action defined for prevent and detect the consequences of the virus. The last step is the proposal of improvements of the concept.

The first step outcome is a tree diagram with all the actors involved. The second step consists in evaluation of the role of each actor. The next step is the analysis of all the possible errors that actors can do. The fourth step is the analysis of the action defined for prevent and detect the consequences of the virus. The last step is the proposal of improvements of the concept.

This paper describes a pandemic risk assessment method that can be used to evaluate the risks associated with a global pandemic situation. The method used for this purpose is Failure Mode and Effect Analysis. Also, in the paper is presented an example of risk evaluation of the concept defined by Romania to deal with Corona virus. Using the classic elements of risk: Severity, Occurrence and Detection all the measures against virus and effects of it are evaluated and prioritized.

The risk assessment of the pandemic plan used by Romanian authorities was performed using the Failure Mode and Effect Analysis – FMEA. The FMEA is a wide used methodology to evaluate and reduce the risks of a design, concept or system (Muntean, Prosteian, Pugna, 2017).

According with VDA standard (Verband der Automobilindustrie) there are five steps followed to create a complete FMEA analysis: structure analysis; function analysis; failure analysis; actions analysis and optimization.

We defined the structure tree presented in figure 1. This was done after the first step, structure definition. The main elements involved in failure chain are: Pandemic effects, Pandemic plan, Management, Control, Spread, Health Care and Communications. These elements of the decision failure chain were identified based on preparedness components defined by World Health Organization – WHO (World Health Organization, 2009).

Figure 1 Tree diagram

The functions, in second step, were defined on three levels: effects, mode and cause, starting with mode level for pandemic plan element. The pandemic plan used must fulfill the functions like:

- Exercises the national pandemic plan
- Revises periodically the national pandemic plan
- Develops the national pandemic plan
- Develops a monitoring system
- Promotes the self-protection
- Prepares the health system to be scale up
- Communicates the risks
- Prevents the virus spread
- Monitors the pandemic operations
- Containments the population
- Activates the emergency plan
- Promotes the recommended interventions
- Mitigates the social and economic impacts
- Assesses the efficiency of the mitigation measures
- Implements the auxiliary social measures
- Implements the emergency plans for health system
- Updates the evolution of the pandemic to all stakeholders
- Manages the additional resources for possible future waves
- Surveillances for possible next waves
- Evaluates the results of the measures used to update the protocols
- Reorganizes the medical system after the peak of the pandemic
- Informs the stakeholders in case of new waves

- Shares the relevant information with international community
- Prepares for next pandemics using the information from the previous ones
- Evaluates all the relevant interventions implemented
- Evaluates the impact of the measures to the health system
- Prepares the communities for next major public health crisis

If all the functions of the pandemic plan are ensured, then the following effects were identified on the level of Pandemic effects system element:

- The pandemic plan reduces the number of people infected
- The pandemic plan reduces the economic effects
- The pandemic plan reduces the social effects

Functions for management decision are:

- Creates a cross-governmental pandemic committee
- Manages the capacities allocated for pandemic situation
- Manages the national organizations involved in pandemic situation
- Updates the national pandemic plan
- Creates the legislation for considered actions
- Facilitates the business continuity planning

Control functions are:

- Develops the national surveillance system
- Assesses the virus transmission risks
- Investigates the illness caused by virus
- Develops the laboratory capabilities

Functions needed for spread control are:

- Promotes the importance of hygiene
- Promotes the control guidance for household
- Supports the ill persons isolated
- Develops plan for class suspension
- Promotes strategies to mitigate the infection in workplaces
- Reduces the travels
- Reduces the mass gatherings
- Estimates the meds requirement
- Develops procedures to provide the meds
- Assesses effectiveness of existing protocols
- Develops a national vaccine action

Functions of health care are:

- Creates a triage system
- Updates the provision strategy for health care
- Develops the management protocols
- Develops the infection control guidance
- Estimates the personal protective equipment
- Develops procedures for laboratory
- Develops the testing capacity

Communication functions are:

- Establishes an emergency communication committee
- Communicates the infection risk status
- Develops an effective relation with media
- Develops communication channels with population
- Develops communication strategies to educate the population
- Initiates public health education campaigns
- Increases public awareness of measures
- Promotes the communication toward disadvantaged persons
- Testes the communications procedures
- Updates the communications strategies

Possible failures or errors were identified for negating each function according with figure 2. This function definition represents the third step of the FMEA methodology. In this step the function and failure net are defined also according with.

The effects identified are presented in figure 2. They are referring to health care of population, social impact and economy. Also, the Severity parameter was assigned to potential failure effects. The most sever effect is rated with 10. No impact or very low impact is rated with 1.

In the fourth step were defined prevention and detection actions like: ordinance in emergency; surveillance; constitutional court decision; World Health Organization measurements; case study from other countries; protocols definition and so on. The Detection and Occurrence values are defined based on considered prevention and detection actions. The best detection/occurrence is rated with 1 and the worst ones with 10.

The outcome of this activity is the actual risk assessment presented in figure 3 and figure 4. The RPN – Risk Priority Number analysis is performed multiplying the Severity, Occurrence and Detection. Based on RPN diagram are identified 14th potential failure causes that must be improved. The biggest RPN value is 900 for potential failure cause: “Does not update the national pandemic plan”. The national pandemic plan is not updated since 2013 and this make the occurrence rating 9. The severity is coming from failure causes effects that is 10. And with no detection actions considered the RPN is 900.

In AP – Action Priority analysis diagram there is another evaluation of risks based on the same three parameters: severity, occurrence and detection. The guideline used is the one from FMEA Handbook (Verband der Automobilindustrie, 2019). There are 19 potential failure causes that have AP value High. For these 19 potential failure causes there are new prevention and detection actions that must be defined.

All these potential failure causes identified as unacceptable risks must be optimized during the fifth step of the FMEA methodology.

Figure 3 RPN analysis

Figure 4 AP analysis

Discussion and conclusions

There are 14 potential failure causes identified as unacceptable risks using the RPN analysis. The biggest RPN value is 900 due to updates mission of the national pandemic plan. All the other risks are associated with weaknesses of the Health Care system and Management.

There are 19 potential failure causes identified with High AP value. Therefore, there are five additional risks identified with AP analysis that are related to the Communication.

These analyses demonstrated also the effectiveness of the new introduced AP evaluation method by identifying more potential unacceptable risks then the previous one RPN.

The analysis of pandemic plan management was done based on 10 military ordnance and the initial fazes of the pandemic situation. The optimization step will be evaluated and implemented in further steps of the pandemic situation.

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